

Deliverable D3.2

Prize Submission Tool

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Contributors	None
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Log of changes

Date	No.	Who	Description
27.10.2022	0.1	Andrew Newman (AE)	First draft documenting the use of the Prize Submission Tool.
28.10.2022	0.2	Veronika Liebl (AE)	Internal review of the deliverable with comments and suggested changes, and the addition of the section outlining the submission help desk.
28.10.2022	0.3	Andrew Newman (AE)	Integration of comments and suggested changes from internal review by Veronika Liebl.
28.10.2022	0.4	Andrea Troncoso (EUSEA)	Comments and suggested changes as part of Quality Assessment.
31.10.2022	1.0	Andrew Neman (AE)	Integration of comments and suggested changes from consortium partner review by Andrea Troncoso (EUSEA). Addition of sections introducing EUPrix and the relationship of the deliverable to other work packages.

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1. Executive Summary

The **Deliverable 3.2 Prize Submission Tool** is aimed at demonstrating the submission tool that has been developed and tested for the European Union Prize for Citizen Science (EUPrix).

The Submission Tool will be used to by applicants to submit entries to the prize, by the Ars Electronica team to review eligibility of submissions, and by the Prize Jury to evaluate submissions to the prize according to the award criteria and select prize winners and honorary mentions.

The Submission Tool

About the European Union Prize for Citizen Science

The **European Union Prize for Citizen Science** acknowledges outstanding achievements in citizen science within the European Research Area and will be awarded in 2023, 2024 and 2025 across three categories.

1. **Grand prize** awarded for outstanding achievements in the field of CS (60.000€);
2. **Diversity & Collaboration Award** for CSIs with explorative collaboration models that actively engage a diverse range of stakeholders and scientific agendas (20.000€);
3. **Digital Communities Award** for exceptional grassroots and community projects (20.000€). Focus will be placed on communities working on digital transformation or advancing the field of CS through digital means.

In addition to these prizes, the jury will select **27 honorary mentions** (without a financial prize) each year, which have helped establish best practices across citizen science.

The first open call for submissions to the EUPrix will be launched on **January 10, 2023** with an initial deadline for submissions for **March 3, 2023** that will be followed by an extended deadline for **March 13, 2023**. For further details concerning the EUPrix consult **D3.1 Prize Working Document**.

2. Deliverable Scope

This deliverable is aimed at demonstrating the prize submission tool and submission database system that has been developed and tested for the European Union Prize for Citizen Science (EUPrix).

This deliverable is the second deliverable within **WP3** and follows the previous deliverable **D3.1 Prize Working Document** and corresponds to **Task 3.1 Prize definition & preparations**. The tool will also play an integral role in supporting the implementation of all other tasks within WP3.

D3.2 Prize Submission Tool			
Work Package No	WP3	Lead Beneficiary	5. AE
Work Package Name	European Union Prize for Citizen Science		
WP3 Start Date	01.07.2022	WP3 End Date	30.06.2026
Corresponding Task	3.1 Prize definition & preparations		
Task 3.1 Start Date	01.08.2022	Task 3.1 End Date	30.11.2022
Other Related Task	3.2 Launch, research, promotion of prize open call		
Task 3.2 Start Date	01.12.2022	Task 3.2 End Date	28.02.2026
Other Related Task	3.3 Evaluation & Jury		
Task 3.3 Start Date	01.03.2023	Task 3.3 End Date	30.04.2026
Other Related Task	3.4 Winner announcement		
Task 3.4 Start Date	01.07.2023	Task 3.4 End Date	30.06.2026

2.1. Contribution to project objectives

The Prize Submission Tool will facilitate the submission and jury selection process for the European Union Prize for Citizen Science. Through providing a stable, secure and user-friendly platform the tool will support the EUPrix's role in fulfilling IMPETUS project's objective: **Recognizing the role of citizen science in Europe**.

3. Prize Submission Tool

The prize submission tool is hosted on the Ars Electronica servers and will go live to the public with the publication of the first open call for submissions to the European Prize for Citizen Science on **January 10, 2023**.

The submission tool will manage several hundred applications that are expected to be submitted to the competition. The EUPrix submission tool builds on and integrates with the existing submission tool developed for the Prix Ars Electronica and has also been previously implemented in other European competitions such as the STARTS Prize. The system has demonstrated its robustness and effectiveness through successfully hosting approximately five thousand prize applications per year. Each year the EUPrix is delivered, the submission tool will be further adapted and updated to respond to any necessary changes in the implementation of the prize or to accommodate any constructive feedback informed by interacting with the tool in the previous year.

3.1. Overview of the submission tool.

For the handling of the submission process of the European Union Prize for Citizen Science an online submission tool based on the expansive Prix Ars Electronica online submission platform was developed to respond to the necessary requirements of the EUPrix.

Prize proposal reception is only possible by using this submission platform and templates without exceptions. Submitters will receive registration information, an acknowledgement of receipt of the submission (to the email address they registered as main contact), information when the call is closed and information on the decision through the platform. Individual qualitative feedback on the evaluation is not foreseen.

At the end of the submission deadline, the system will automatically close and not accept any further submissions.

3.2. GDPR and Data Collection through the Open Call

All data will be stored on servers of Ars Electronica and monitored by the Data Security Group of Ars Electronica following GDPR conformity. Consent for data sharing and long-term preservation are included in the submission questionnaires dealing with personal data. The EUPrix explicitly foresees a strict Data Protection Policy, which information is part of the submission

process. Specifics on the EUPrix strategy in the handling of data will be laid out in detail in Deliverable 1.2 Data Management Plan.

3.3. Architecture of the submission tool.

The EUPrix submission tool offers three different viewpoints according to which user is utilizing the platform.

The **Submitter View** is accessible to applicants after they have signed up on the open call platform. Here they can enter their projects and personal data, arrange the materials for their projects and officially submit the finished entries for consideration for the EUPrix.

The **Team View** is used by the team handling and managing the uploads. The team may add information, data and assets that were forgotten by the

submitter, they can see metadata about the project and they can add comments and other useful information into the database. The team can also handle the jury members and assign them to projects and in a further step manage the jury process by finalizing single assessment rounds and assigning Nominations, Honorary Mentions and the two special award categories and the Grand Prize to the winning projects.

The **Jury View** is dedicated to create an easy access and overview for the jury members. The jury can see all the projects that are admitted to the jury process and with one click are able to view all the public details of any given project such as the description and uploaded materials as well as the biographical data of the project's authors.

3.4. Submitter View

The submitters sign up with their contacts on the main entry page. After they have validated their email address, they can enter one or more projects for consideration for the EUPrix.

The following screenshots show the layout that submitters will encounter and the field to be filled in for a standard submission.

3.4.1. Start Page

Figure 1. Submitter View – Start Page

EUROPEAN UNION PRIZE FOR
CITIZEN SCIENCE

[Sign up](#) or [Log in](#)

European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2023!

Welcome to the European Union Prize for Citizen Science 2023!

You can submit your free online submission here.
Please check the EUPrix open call site and get started with your Sign up process!

[Sign up](#) or [Log in](#)

ARS ELECTRONICA
AIT, Technology & Society

EUSEA
EUROPEAN UNION PRIZE FOR CITIZEN SCIENCE

KING'S COLLEGE LONDON

nestA

Science for Change

SUCCESS SYSTEMS

zabala
INNOVATION

IMPETUS

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With questions about content and/or technical questions, please contact: @ars.electronica.art

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3.4.2. Registration Page

Prize applicants must register their personal details within the registration before they can submit an initiative to the competition.

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Figure 2. Submitter View – Registration Page

[My Projects](#)
Citizen Science Test Subject
Log

Email address*

First name* Last name*

Gender* Nationality*

Address*

Postal code* City*

State Country*

Phonenumber*

Contact Type Contact + Add

Newsletter: Would you like to get info about Ars Electronica's activities conveniently and on a regular basis?
You have the right to revoke your consent at any time by sending an e-mail to that effect to dsk@ars.electronica.art. A revocation option will also be appended to every communiqué you receive from us from now on.

Save changes

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3.4.3. Add Project Page

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Applicants can enter multiple initiatives to the EUPrix and can add the details for each submission by adding each initiative as a project within the Add Project Page.

Figure 3. Submitter View – Add Project Page

The screenshot shows the 'My Projects' section of the submission tool. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the 'EUROPEAN UNION PRIZE FOR CITIZEN SCIENCE' logo, a 'My Projects' link, a user profile for 'Citizen Science Test Subject', and a 'Log' button. Below this, the 'My Projects' section features a '+ Add Project' button and a table of existing projects.

Title	Started at	Actions	Status
New Initiative	Oct. 28, 2022, 12:30 a.m.	Preview Edit Upload	Incomplete
Citizen Science Initiative	Oct. 27, 2022, 11:55 p.m.	Preview Edit Upload	Incomplete

Below the table, there is a row of partner logos including ARS ELECTRONICA, EUSEA, KINGS College LONDON, nesta, Science for Change, MICROSYSTEMS, and zabala INNOVATION. The IMPETUS logo and 'Funded by the European Union' logo are also present. A disclaimer text follows, stating that the prize is delivered within the IMPETUS project framework and that the views expressed are those of the author(s).

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3.4.4. Edit Project Page

Applicants can edit the details for the initiative they would like to submit to the prize within the Edit Project Page. Core data about each project is collected on the edit tab of the platform. Here all necessary information is entered and missing information is highlighted in a bright red frame.

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Figure 4. Submitter View – Edit Project Details Page 1/2

My Projects
Citizen Science Test Subject
Log

Save
To do
Preview
Edit
Upload
Incomplete

Project

Title of the Initiative *

Location of Initiative

Timeframe of Initiative

Abstract *

Please fill out this field.

Description *

Please fill out this field.

Research question *

Please fill out this field.

Initiative team *

Please fill out this field.

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Figure 5. Submitter View – Edit Project Details Page 2/2

Citizen engagement *

Please fill out this field.

How will the prize money benefit your community? *

Please fill out this field.

URL

Username/Password

+

-

Credit

Support received from

Applicants can upload assets such as images, PDFs or videos in the upload section. The order of the assets can be changed by drag-and-drop and comments can be added to each item.

Figure 6. Submitter View – Upload Asset

Upload is successfully done. Once the conversion process is complete, you can check the video in the "Preview" section. (You don't have to wait for the video conversion to submit your project).

Preview Edit Upload Incomplete

New Initiative

Choose a file or Drag it here.

Browse... Video Gruppe 2 Lego.mp4

- Upload of maximum 15 assets allowed.
- Please upload at least 1 video and a few images
- The following file formats are supported: .jpg, .gif, .png, .tiff, .pdf, .mp4, .wav
- The recommended video formats are: container mp4 with H264 codec, audio stereo with 16 Bit and 44,1 kHz
- With the "Preview" page, you can check how your submission looks like.
- Your uploaded video is converted automatically, and it takes a few hours to be shown in the "Preview" page.
- You can change the order of the uploaded material afterwards by using drag & drop

Select all Delete selected

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3.4.6. Preview Project Page

Applicants have the chance to preview what their projects will look like to the jury by accessing the preview tab in the database. This is the same view jury members have when assessing submissions.

Figure 7. Submitter View – Preview My Project Page

Project Artists

Location of Initiative Austria, Europe	Timeframe of Initiative 2022 - 2024
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Abstract
IMPETUS will support and give recognition to citizen science (CS) by enabling a wider range of citizen science initiatives (CSIs) to access innovative funding. We aim to bring CS closer to society and policymakers and to acknowledge its role in tackling the greatest challenges of our times. We will have a strong focus on enhancing its contributions to the Green Deal and the UN SDGs.

Description
3 Open Calls, selecting the initiatives based on expected impacts, volunteer engagement, EDI, openness and quality data. We will offer 20k to kick-start 100 CSIs and 10k to sustain 25 CSIs addressing the pressing needs of European society. Setting up an accelerator that will provide an integrated programme of support, training, mentoring, and resources. The accelerator will facilitate peer learning, enable CSIs to contribute to UN SDG and GD targets and forge connections with quadruple helix stakeholders. Launching the EU Prize for Citizen Science, awarded to CSIs for outstanding achievements, allowing them to continue and expand their work and showcase it to a broader audience. We will award 3 prize categories for 3 years: outstanding achievements, diversity and innovative grassroots projects. Each time, we will reach out to advisors to identify exceptional nominations and to the citizen panel to vote in the grassroots category. Convening a citizen panel that provides feedback on our work. Shaping EU policy in and with CS, through horizon scanning, anticipatory policy and action research, informing policy briefs, webinars and workshops with key policy stakeholders. The aim is to foster more CS data to inform evidence-based policies and identify future directions in CS policy. Developing impact assessment tools and assessing the impact of CSIs and our own framework, especially on GD and SDG targets. Insights will be presented within the wider CS ecosystem and feed into recommendations for national and EU policies.

Research question
This WP will set up an impact-driven citizen science accelerator to support the CSI selected in the open calls of WP1 (pilots), empowering them to maximize their scientific, social, economic, democratic, and environmental impacts towards the SDGs and the GD targets.

Initiative team
Ars Electronica has sought out interlinkages and congruities, causes and effects on the nexus of art, technology, and society since its inception in 1970. The Festival as proving ground, the Prix as competition honoring excellence, the Center as a permanent setting for presentation & interaction, and the Futurelab and Ars Electronica Solutions as in-house R&D facilities extending their feelers throughout the realms of science and research, art and technology. Ars Electronica's divisions inspire one another and put futuristic visions to the test in a unique, creative feedback loop. Ars Electronica is the leading partner responsible for delivering the the European Union Prize for Citizen Science. The prize gives recognition to Citizen Science Initiatives for outstanding achievements, allowing them to continue and expand their work and showcase it to a wider audience.

Citizen engagement
EUSEA is an international community of public engagement professionals, science festival and science event organizers. The association comprises about 120 members, including universities and scientific institutions, science festival organisations, science centres and museums, municipalities and NGOs. The network has developed from a knowledge-sharing platform for European science festivals to a collaborative community of public engagement professionals, developing and testing new formats of science communication, building relationships with researchers, policy-makers and stakeholders from scientific institutions, higher education institutions, municipalities and regions. EUSEA is the initiator of the European Science Engagement Platform, a resource of recommendations, best practices and innovative event formats for practitioners working in the field of science-society dialogues.

Community benefit.
Nesta's Centre for Collective Intelligence Design works with methods that bring together diverse groups of people, with new sources of data and digital technologies to find solutions to society's biggest problems. Their work focuses on developing tools and projects for the benefit of communities, and on helping institutions strengthen trust and collaboration with citizens. Nesta's Collective Intelligence Design Playbook helped to define the field and is used by practitioners around the world. In Impetus, Nesta leads the policy engagement activities with a focus on inclusion, improving data practices and localising the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) and Green Deal targets. They will also develop training materials and design resources to help citizen science practitioners maximise their impact, which will be trialed with participants in the Accelerator Programme.

URLs of the project
<https://impetus4cs.eu/>

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Once all obligatory information has been added by the applicant, the Submit button appears. By hitting the submit button, the project is finalized and added to the submitted projects in the database. The applicant then receives an email confirmation that their prize has been successfully submitted.

3.5. Team View

Upon entering the database, the team view gives the team members a quick overview of the submission status of the different categories. From here, submitted projects can be easily managed. Team members can access every project to add assets of information if necessary. Admin members can manage and add jury members and the jury process from the miscellaneous tab in the overview.

3.6. Jury View

Jury Members will access the database with their individual passwords and have access to all the approved projects eligible for the EUPrix in the form of a list. They will be able to see comments left by the team, as well as an overview on information when they first enter the database.

EUROPEAN UNION PRIZE FOR CITIZEN SCIENCE

Andrew Newman
Log out

 Export current table

Digital Communities | Jury round: | Yes/No: | For STARTS only:

Show entries

Showing 1 to 15 of 15 entries

Search:

ClosedID	Initiative	Jury	Yes/No	Applicant	Gender	Location	Subcatego	Year	Starts	Annotation	Duration
2022_DC_0118	All the Stars We Cannot See	Rashmi Dhanwani	---	Yujie Gao, Megan Smith	f, f	CN, CA	Social Software	2020	✓	Rashmi Dhanwani Art+science project harnessing public data on space, bringing awareness and access to this data, and involving communities in dialogue around it.	
2022_DC_0154	Alsaha Archive		---	Akhbar ElSaha		M	Community Project	2020		Rashmi Dhanwani Archival project from Lebanon, documenting revolution and post-revolution demonstrations and people's uprisings. Independant, anonymous and nuanced. Carla Gimeno Grauwinkel Recommended by Jury member Farah Saika	
2022_DC_0245	Blank Noise	Sarah Kriesche	---	Jasmeen Patheja	f	IN	Community Project	2003	✓	Carla Gimeno Grauwinkel Recommended by Advisors Erandy Vergara & Maren Richter	
2022_DC_0087	Center for Political Beauty		---	Philipp Ruch	m	DE	Other	2021		Carla Gimeno Grauwinkel Recommended by Jury member Simon Weckert	
2022_DC_0157	Commons Cargobikes	Rashmi Dhanwani	---	Commons Cargobike Initiatives , wlelebenwir e.V.	,	M, DE	Community Project	2013	✓	Rashmi Dhanwani Excellent example of open source driven ideas, boosted by share-ability, achieving urban and policy impact.	
2022_DC_0224	Families For Freedom	Rashmi Dhanwani	---	Amina Khouliani	f	SY	Other	2017		Carla Gimeno Grauwinkel Recommended by Farah Saika	
2022_DC_0031	FragDenStaat	Thomas Gegenhuber	---	Arne Semsrott	m	DE	Social Software	2011			
2022_DC_0204	Internet Freedom Foundation		---	Ashlesh Balaji Biraadar	m	IN	Community Project	2016		Carla Gimeno Grauwinkel Recommended by Jury member Rashmi Dhanwani	
2022_DC_0206	SalvageGarden: Computers Against Covid	Simon Weckert	---	saad chinoy	m	IN	Community Project	2020	✓	Carla Gimeno Grauwinkel Recommended	

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Once the jury members click on any project, the individual project pages will open, showing the materials added, the author information as well as any annotations added by the team in the meantime.

3.7. Submission Help Desk

Both the IMPETUS website as well as the submission platform will specify contact information for technical help and questions. This will be a general email address citizenscience@ars.electronica.art, operated on workdays daily between 10am-4pm (Brussels time) and during the weekend before the submission deadline. Ars Electronica will be responsible for managing this email address.

4. Conclusion

As illustrated within this deliverable the Prize Submission Tool for the European Union Prize for Citizen Science has been successfully installed and tested. The submission tool will undergo two more test phases in November 2022 and during this period has the capacity to adapt any changes that are necessary to implement feedback from the Project Officer corresponding to **D3.1 Prize Working Document**.

The prize submission tool will be hosted on the Ars Electronica servers but will be linked to the Open Call for Submissions to the European Prize for Citizen Science on both the Ars Electronica website and the Impetus project website. The submission tool will go live to the public with the publication of the first open call on **January 10, 2023**.